

From cave buffer zones to protected areas: speleology data management with free and open-source software (FOSS)

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Abstract

The field of speleology is dependent upon the accurate mapping and analysis of data to gain an understanding of subterranean environments. Free and open-source software (FOSS) has facilitated advancements in spatial data management, offering robust tools for data collection, analysis, and fieldwork. Software solutions such as PostgreSQL with PostGIS, QGIS, GRASS, and QField facilitate efficient geospatial data management and data collection. The accurate location determination of caves is of paramount importance, given their significant ecological, historical, and cultural value. In Brazil, the implementation of rigorous environmental legislation has resulted in the establishment of a 250-meter buffer zone surrounding caves. This regulatory measure is designed to ensure the protection of these vulnerable ecosystems and to regulate activities within their vicinity. The radius may be modified based on the findings of environmental studies, thereby ensuring the preservation of caves while facilitating socio-economic development. This study presents EspeleoVale, a software as a service (SaaS) solution hosted on AWS. It employs open-source scripting languages and frameworks, including AngularJS, PostgreSQL with PostGIS, and MapStore2 integrated with Geoserver, to effectively manage and visualize speleological data for a mining company in Brazil. By employing SQL queries and spatial functions, users can visualize cave locations and their restricted areas, thereby facilitating the assessment of project impacts on these geomorphological features. In this study, examples of visualization and spatial analysis are presented for five hypothetical caves and a hypothetical project, returning intersections, differences and merged areas, which are vital for the environmental protection of cavities and for knowing project restrictions. Thus, the integration of an RDBMS for spatial analysis and FOSS tools for data visualization fosters new developments and promotes more efficient speleology data management.

1. Introduction

1.1 Free open-source software for speleology

Speleology is a field of study that relies heavily on the accurate mapping and analysis of data. Understanding subterranean environments requires the use of extensive spatial data, which can be difficult to manage and illustrate (Palmer, 2015).

Over time, free and open-source software (FOSS) has gained considerable traction, facilitating advancements in spatial data management through the processes of collection, analysis, and distribution (Petković, 2016). FOSS provides robust tools for the management, analysis, and fieldwork of data. Projects such as PostgreSQL with the PostGIS extension facilitate efficient geospatial data management, providing a robust foundation for the storage and querying of cave-related datasets (<https://www.postgresql.org/>). QGIS (<https://www.qgis.org/>) and GRASS GIS (<https://grass.osgeo.org/>) provide the necessary tools for advanced spatial analysis and mapping, which is essential for understanding the relationship between cave systems and the surface environment. In the context of fieldwork, QField offers a seamless integration with QGIS, thereby enabling speleologists to collect and analyze survey data in real time. Furthermore, dedicated speleology-focused projects, such as Survex (<https://github.com/ojwb/survex>), play a pivotal role in cave mapping, offering specialized tools that are tailored to the intricacies of underground environments.

The convergence of general-purpose FOSS tools with speleology-specific applications presents a unique opportunity to develop bespoke solutions for cave exploration and research. For instance, FOSS is already being employed to assess geological hazards (Baiocchi *et al.*, 2021) and hydrogeological vulnerability (Duarte *et al.*, 2019; Ollivier *et al.*, 2019), applications that could be directly adapted for speleological studies.

In Brazil, several studies have been conducted to promote the use of geographic information systems (GIS) as a means of managing, analyzing, and visualizing speleology data (Simões & Pereira Filho, 2003; Araujo *et al.*, 2011). This is further supported by the necessity of accurately recording and comprehensively understanding the locations of caves, given their significant ecological, historical, and cultural value (Gillieson, 2021). The federal agency known as Instituto Chico Mendes de Conservação da Biodiversidade (ICMBIO) has established a repository called Cadastro Nacional de Informações Espeleológicas – CANIE, created by Resolução CONAMA N° 347/2004, which contains over 20,000 cave locations and attributes (BRASIL, 2004). Furthermore, this legislation establishes protections for speleological formations, which are intrinsically linked to their locations (BRASIL, 2004).

1.2 Speleology regulations and particularities

In Brazil, environmental legislation establishes comprehensive guidelines for activities in proximity to speleological formations, thereby ensuring that any land use or development in the vicinity of cave systems is subject to meticulous regulation (BRASIL, 1990). In essence, these regulations are designed to safeguard these vulnerable ecosystems, underscoring the necessity for precise location determination to ensure effective protection.

Brazilian legislation requires the establishment of a 250-meter radius buffer zone around any cave, within which any potentially damaging activities are strictly regulated or prohibited (BRASIL, 1990; IBAMA, 1990). Subsequently, it was determined that the radius could be modified based on the findings of environmental studies, including the delineation of the water contribution basin, the assessment of cave nutrient supply, and the mapping of underground cave connectivity. Furthermore, environmental impact studies are conducted to ensure the integrity of the cave

and its surrounding area (BRASIL, 2004). Additionally, caves situated in proximity may be grouped and afforded the same level of protection within a designated area. This flexible approach allows for the reconciliation of conservation goals with socio-economic development, provided that the cave's preservation remains uncompromised.

Considering the critical importance of cave locations and their associated areas, as well as the evolving nature of the data pertaining to them, it is imperative that a reliable software architecture be in place to ensure the effective management and visualization of speleological data. This study aims to present a FOSS implementation using PostgreSQL/PostGIS for speleology data management, PostGIS for spatial analysis and Geoserver/Mapstore2 for spatial data visualization in a speleological context.

2. Material and methods

VALE, a Brazilian mining company, primarily engages in the exploitation of iron ore in two regions: Carajás and Quadrilátero Ferrífero. These areas are characterized by a high concentration of iron speleological formations, with over 6,000 documented occurrences. In order to facilitate the organization and analysis of this vast amount of data, the company has developed a relational database to catalog and store the information (Araujo *et al.*, 2011).

VALE entrusted Tetra Tech with the development of a software as a service (SaaS) solution, named EspeleoVale, which integrated free and open-source software (FOSS) technologies to provide a comprehensive speleology data management platform. The platform is hosted on Amazon Web Services (AWS), and its primary architecture employs open-source scripting languages, including JavaScript, HTML, CSS, GO, and SQL. The architectural components and frameworks include AngularJS, PostgreSQL relational database management system (RDBMS) with the PostGIS extension, and Mapstore2 integrated with Geoserver.

The Database Management System (DBMS) PostgreSQL permits the storage of alphanumeric attributes in a relational database. The PostGIS extension enables the storage of geometry information and the utilization of a suite of spatial functions. A front-end layer is anticipated above the database. Languages such as JavaScript, CSS, and HTML, integrated with the AngularJS framework, facilitate the integration of user input data with the backend and the database.

In consideration of the spatial characteristics of the data, the open-source server Geoserver and the Mapstore2 mapping framework are suitable for the publication and visualization of cave locations and protected areas. Additionally, Mapstore2 offers built-in features such as dashboards and geostories, which can be utilized to present qualitative and quantitative data.

The FOSS technologies are designed to capitalize on the potential of new developments, implementations, and customizations, enabling the fulfillment of specific needs without being constrained by the limitations inherent to proprietary software (Moreno-Sanchez & Brovelli, 2023). In this study, a SQL query was performed in the RDBMS to facilitate the visualization of disparate representations of cave locations. Subsequently, a new application was developed using PostGIS pre-built functions, whereby the user can input a region of interest and ascertain the overlap of cave geometries and its restrictions in relation to the project layout.

The SQL query strategy employed a multi-column approach incorporating geometry data (Table 1). Consequently, cave instances with their attributes can have three spatial representations of their location, including **initial coordinates** returned by prospection studies, **topography coordinates**, and **cave topography**, both of which are returned by topographical surveys (Figure 1). The locations of these caves are bounded by a restriction area, known as **restricted areas**, which were initially set as 250-meter buffers from the location feature (point or polygon). These buffers were also included as geometry columns.

Figure 1. Different spatial representations of cave locations

cave	general attributes	geom_ini_coord	geom_top_coord	geom_topography
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Table 1. Example of SQL view headers

Following the organization of the data, the view was published in Geoserver as a layer and a SLD style was applied, thus enabling the presentation of cave locations and their restricted areas in multiple formats. The SLD code was implemented using the Geoserver SLD viewer.

As previously stated in the introduction, the restricted area may be modified from a 250-meter buffer zone to a clearly delineated restricted area. The area may undergo an increase or decrease in size, including a change in shape. The procedure for updating the restricted area of caves is to upload a geometry file (polygon) to the EspeleoVale application and select the caves associated with that polygon. A relational database foreign key reference is employed to register the relationship between caves and their restricted areas. To visualize the restricted areas on a map, the features are grouped by restricted area ID and cave identification, and other attributes are concatenated.

Once the locations of the caves and their protection area have been defined, EspeleoVale can then promote development opportunities based on the restricted areas for the development of activities, as determined by the evaluation of the projects in question. Consequently, Tetra Tech devised a novel functionality that enables users to specify a region of interest (ROI), which is typically associated with a project. By leveraging user input, the RDBMS scans for intersections between cave buffers and the ROI, and if any are identified, the RDBMS executes spatial analysis operations and records the outcomes in the database.

The principal functions include ST_Buffer, ST_Union, and ST_Intersection, which are used to ascertain which caves and their buffers overlap the region of interest (ROI) and subsequently aggregate those geometries, thereby returning a merged buffer feature and a defined area feature. Subsequently, the application performs ST_Difference to obtain the difference between the merged buffer zones and the defined restricted areas, and ST_Intersection to obtain this difference within the ROI. The resulting analyses return new geometries, categorized as merged

buffers, defined restricted areas, total difference area, and ROI. The geometries and area quantities are stored in the database using the same multi-column strategy.

3. Results and discussion

Given the sensitivity of proprietary information, we present examples of hypothetical projects and caves to illustrate the application in this study. Five caves (IM_0001, IM_0002, IM_0003, IM_0004, and IM_0005) were considered in the region of Ilha de Marajó, near Belém, Pará, Brazil (Figure 2). As indicated in the Figure 2, all five caves exhibit three distinct geometries (initial coordinates – orange dot, topography coordinates – green dot, and topography – gray area). Each geometry is represented by a specific color, which denotes the restricted area (250m buffer). The snapshot was obtained from Mapstore2, which enables users to click, zoom in, and view the attribute table for these caves (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Different types of caves geometries and its buffer zones

Figure 3. Caves and its attribute table presented in Mapstore2

Of the five caves, three (IM_0001, IM_0002, IM_0003) were found to be of equal relevance through the course of the studies, and thus were designated as a singular feature with a defined

restricted area (Figure 4). The remaining two caves possess their own distinct defined restricted areas (Figure 4).

The aforementioned areas are subject to activity restrictions, which represent a significant environmental protection measure. Companies intending to implement projects are required to certify the integrity of the area of influence of the caves in question and to confirm that they have not considered restricted areas in their project designs.

Defined restricted areas

- Defined restricted area
- Polygon
- 250m Buffer - Polygon
- 250m Buffer - Initial coordinates
- 250m Buffer - Topography coordinates
- Initial coordinates
- Topography coordinates

Figure 4. Defined restricted areas.

A hypothetical Environmental Laboratory for Biodiversity Studies is considered for the region described above. Its design, in vector format (polygon), was entered into EspeleoVale as the region of interest (ROI). As presented in Figure 5, the ROI intersects the buffer of all five caves listed previously. This results in the trigger being fired to perform the spatial analysis and register new geometries and areas in the database.

The merged buffers yielded a total of 44.5 hectares, which is presented as a gray outline in Figure 5. The resulting area for all restricted areas is 16.8 hectares, which yields a total difference area of 27.7 hectares (orange representation). The total difference area that intersects with the ROI (green polygon) represents 9.11 hectares. Figure 5 illustrates that despite a reduction in restricted areas, there are still defined restricted areas (red polygons)

intersecting the ROI, necessitating alterations to the project design.

Figure 5. Example of the spatial analysis feature

The incorporation of a RDBMS for spatial analysis, coupled with GeoServer and MapStore2 for the publication and visualization of speleological features, markedly enhances user interaction and facilitates more efficient speleology data management. The findings concur with those of preceding studies that employed free and open-source software (FOSS) to store, analyze, and visualize speleological data. Examples include the geological and geomorphological features study conducted in Andalusia, Spain (Suma & Cosmo, 2011), and the collection and storage of spatial and non-spatial information on Turkish caves in a relational database (Erbas, 2020).

4. Conclusions

This study demonstrates the significant potential of integrating free and open-source software (FOSS) technologies for the effective management and visualization of speleological data. By leveraging tools such as PostgreSQL/PostGIS for data management, and GeoServer/MapStore2 for spatial data visualization, the EspeleoVale platform provides a robust solution for handling the complexities of cave data. This integration not only enhances user interaction but also ensures that critical environmental protections are maintained, aligning with the stringent regulations governing speleological formations in Brazil. The ability to perform real-time spatial analysis and visualize cave locations and their restricted areas facilitates informed decision-making, promoting both conservation and development goals.

In conclusion, the implementation of FOSS technologies in speleology offers a flexible and cost-effective approach to managing and analyzing spatial data. The case study of EspeleoVale highlights the practical applications of these technologies in a real-world context, demonstrating their capacity to support comprehensive environmental assessments and project planning. As the field of speleology continues to

evolve, the adoption of such innovative solutions will be crucial in addressing the challenges of data management and environmental protection, ensuring the sustainable exploration and preservation of subterranean environments.

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